

Multi-Depth Soil Moisture Monitoring Within A Single- And Dual- Axis Tracking Agrivoltaic System In Brandenburg, North-Eastern Germany

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Introduction

- Agrivoltaic (AV) systems alter the microclimate, rainfall distribution, and solar radiation, impacting soil moisture dynamics.
- Soil moisture is crucial for crop productivity in sandy soils; low values lead to drought stress and yield loss.
- A better understanding of these effects is key to optimizing crop performance under AV conditions.

Fig. 1: ZALF-Agri-PV. Left) UAV image (17.06.2025) showing both the tracking AV system and the alfalfa stand (© M. Donat). Right) Soil preparation with a cultivator (01.04.2025) (© L. Richter).

Objectives

- Design of a spatially adapted sensor layout tailored to AV infrastructure and shading patterns.
- Analysis of spatial-temporal soil temperature and moisture dynamics under AV systems at multiple soil depths.

Methods

- AV site (since 12/2024): 580 kWp single- and dual-axis tracking system (0.5 ha and 0.2 ha and a total of 832 panels) located at ZALF, Müncheberg.
- 75 soil sensors (moisture, temperature, electrical conductivity) installed at 25 locations (3 depths) in AV with additional sensors in adjacent control plots.

Fig. 2: Sensor layout. Left) UAV image (26.11.2024) of single-axis tracking AV system and installation of multi-parameter soil monitoring systems. Center) Soil sensors and visualization of depth. Right) Sensor layout of both systems. (All images © M. Donat)

Fig. 3: Important factors that influence the soil moisture. A) Soil electrical conductivity (S. Koszinski). B) Digital Terrain Model. C) Slope D) Digital Surface Model E) Potential reduction of solar radiation due to adjacent woody area at ground level (modeled for the month of April).

Results

Fig. 4: Daily precipitation and soil moisture values of first point within first transect

Initial high soil moisture levels at 45 cm declined quickly. Soil moisture was consistently higher in deeper layers than in upper layers. Moisture responded to precipitation at all depths (due to sandy soils - loamy sand). Soil moisture values have been declining at all depths since march. Total precipitation during the period of 178 days amounted to 157 mm.

Fig. 5: Air and soil temperatures from three neighboring transect_1 points (center row) and the control. Left) Temperatures and their variations in 2025; the vertical line visualizes the DOY 125 (section on the right). Right) Section from DOY 125 for the same sensors and the air temperature at 2m and 5 cm heights (outside the AV).

Fig. 6: Daily changes in soil moisture at a depth of 45 cm in the single-axis AV system. Left) Daily changes in mean soil moisture along the eastern strip throughout the year. Right) Boxplot of all soil moisture sensors at 45 cm within the "center" measurement strip.

Outlook

- Optimize energy and crop yields through a multi-modeling framework.
- Link soil, AV tracking, weather, and crop development data for modeling and decision support.
- Evaluate shading effects on soil to improve crop management in AV systems.

Fig. 7: Concept for energy and crop optimization.

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